

Six New Combinations in *Arrojadoa*, *Echinocereus*, *Eriosyce*, *Kadenicarpus* and *Opuntia* (Cactaceae)

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Abstract—The new combinations *Arrojadoa eddie-estevesii*, *Arrojadoa pusilliflora*, *Echinocereus ×roetteri* subsp. *kunzei*, *Eriosyce lichyi*, *Kadenicarpus pseudomacrochele* nothosubsp. *kubesii* and *Opuntia tehuantepecana* are proposed.

Arrojadoa eddie-estevesii (P.J.Braun) M.H.J.van der Meer **comb. nov.** ≡ *Pierrebraunia eddie-estevesii* P.J.Braun (in *Kakteen* And. Sukk. 68(12): 319. 2017).

Arrojadoa pusilliflora (F.Ritter) M.H.J.van der Meer **comb. nov.** ≡ *Floribunda pusilliflora* F.Ritter ([Kakteen Südamerika 1: 58. 1979](#)).

Echinocereus ×roetteri subsp. *kunzei* (Gürke) M.H.J.van der Meer **comb. et stat. nov.** ≡ *Echinocereus ×kunzei* Gürke (in [Monatsschr. Kakteenk. 17: 103. 1907](#)).
Parentage: *Echinocereus coccineus* Engelm. × *Echinocereus dasyacanthus* Engelm. in Wisl.

Eriosyce lichyi (Matusz. & Kupčák) M.H.J.van der Meer **comb. nov.** ≡ *Pyrrhocactus lichyi* Matusz. & Kupčák (in *CactusWorld* 41(4): 327. 2023).

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Kadenicarpus pseudomacrochele nothosubsp. kubesii (Halda & Kupčák) M.H.J.van der Meer **comb. nov.** \equiv *Turbinicarpus* \times *kubesii* (“*kubesii*”) Halda & Kupčák (in [Acta Mus. Richnov., Sect. Nat. 7\(2\): 76. 2000](#)). Parentage: *Kadenicarpus pseudomacrochele* subsp. *krainzianus* (Gerhart Frank) Vázquez-Sánchez \times *Kadenicarpus pseudomacrochele* (Backeb.) Doweld subsp. *pseudomacrochele*.

Opuntia tehuantepecana (Bravo ex S.Arias) Bravo ex M.H.J.van der Meer **comb. nov.** \equiv *Opuntia dillenii* var. *tehuantepecana* Bravo ex S.Arias (in *Cact. Suc. Mex.* 37: 74. 1992) = *Opuntia dillenii* var. *tehuantepecana* Bravo (in [Cact. Suc. Mex. 9\(3\): 55-57. 1964](#)), nom. inval. (art. 40.1, type not designated) = *Opuntia tehuantepecana* (Bravo) Bravo (in [Cact. Suc. Mex. 17\(4\): 119. 1972](#) [basionym citation as “*Cact. Suc. Mex.* 9: 55. 1969”]), nom. inval. (art. 6.10, basionym not validly published).

